

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Oryza minuta is not endemic to the Philippines

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The diploid species *Oryza officinalis* and tetraploid species *O. minuta* have been confused in the literature. The two species, however, can be clearly distinguished on the basis of spikelet dimension, panicle structure, and habit.

Herbarium studies show *O. minuta* had previously been found only in the Philippines. *O. officinalis* is widely distributed from India to Papua New Guinea. On the islands of the Malay archipelago, it has been collected in Sabah, Sarawak, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Sumatra, Java, Halmahera, Bacan Island, and Western Province of Papua New Guinea.

We report finding several populations of *O. minuta* (see figure) around Wasua village (08:20S latitude, 142:50E longitude) in Western Province, Papua New Guinea. The stoloniferous species was growing, either in shade or partial sunlight, beside a small creek in sago swamps. We did not find *O. officinalis* in the area, but did collect it along the south coast of Western Province.

Spikelets of *O. minuta* populations in the Philippines are thicker than those of populations collected in Papua New Guinea (see table). □

Distribution of *Oryza minuta* (▼).

Spikelet dimensions of *Oryza minuta*.

Collection no.	Site	Spikelet dimension ^a (mm)		
		Length	Width	Thickness
<i>Philippines</i>				
P90-1	Luzon	4.7	1.8	1.4
P90-6	Samar	4.5	1.8	1.3
P90-17	Leyte	4.8	1.9	1.2
P90-19	Southern Leyte	4.7	1.8	1.4
<i>Papua New Guinea</i>				
91PNG-17	Western Province	4.5	1.9	0.9
91PNG-18	Western Province	4.2	1.9	0.9
91PNG-19	Western Province	4.5	2.0	1.0
91PNG-20	Western Province	4.7	2.0	1.0

^aMean of 10 measurements per population.

Breeding methods

Identification of promising CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines for developing Philippine rice hybrids

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Five cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines obtained from IRRI were evaluated at three locations in the Philippines for pollen sterility, spikelet fertility of bagged panicles, field reaction to rice tungro virus, and days to 50% flowering.

Stable CMS lines were V20 A and IR46830 A (both with CMS-WA cytoplasm), and IR54755 A (CMS-ARC cytoplasm). CMS lines IR58025 A and

IR62829 A were nearly stable for male sterility (Table 1).

IR54755 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A showed slight to no infection with tungro viruses. Outcrossing potential of IR62829 A, IR58025 A, and V20 A was acceptable. CMS lines flowered at 81-102 d at IRRI, but at 102-116 d at Banaue (high altitude, lower temperature). IR58025 A and IR62829 A